

WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

Deliverable 1.2: Database on Availability of Agri-Environmental Indices in Member States at NUTS3, and Options for Data Collection at Farm Scale

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	1: Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers
Deliverable	Deliverable 1.2: database on availability of agri-environmental indices in MS at NUTS3, and options for data collection at farm scale
Date of report	December 2024
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DigitAF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°101059794. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

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0 SUMMARY

The European Union dearly needs ways to evaluate the success of environmental and climate measures. Currently, each country, legal framework or sector uses its own indicators, and the data, although partly collected at the local level, is often reported only as aggregated data, at the scale of countries (NUTS0). This prevents local decision-makers or practitioners from using this data, in particular when assessing the impact of implementing agroecological levers such as agroforestry. Therefore, the aim of this report is to identify environmental data that can be used at more local levels (NUTS 4-5) and to provide suggestions on how to improve data collection, aggregation and dissemination in order to provide locally relevant, consistent and reliable data to stakeholders.

Among the five legal frameworks that we analysed, we identified 14 indicator categories (28 individual indicators) relevant to assess the impact of agroforestry, and identified some of their shortcomings: (i) mixing afforestation and agroforestry, (ii) considering only newly established AF systems and not their maintenance, (iii) reporting agroforestry as several different measures (all mixed with other levers), making it impossible to use the data to estimate the area under agroforestry, (iv) not having agroforestry as an option when separating arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland and (v) last but not least, not considering a large number of the beneficial effects of agroforestry that would be relevant for other objectives (besides environment) such as fair income, rural areas, food and health.

Twelve existing impact indicators have been identified as most relevant for farm-scale monitoring of the impact of agroforestry and landscape features. These are:

- **I.9 Improving the resilience of agriculture to climate change:** includes a) agriculture income stability, b) crop production stability for cereals, c) water exploitation index, d) soil organic carbon in agricultural land - only available at NUTS 1 or NUTS 2 (region) level.
- **I.10 Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture:** uses national GHG emission calculations which vary greatly and are usually published only at a national level (NUTS 0). Only a few member states estimate the impact of woody vegetation separately.
- **I.11 Enhancing carbon sequestration:** based on the LUCAS soil survey therefore not available at farm or parcel scale. Averaged to NUTS2
- **I.12 Increasing sustainable energy in agriculture** - agroforestry can contribute to this, but the indicator is published at national (NUTS 0) scale
- **I.13 Reducing soil erosion:** scale is different between countries. Usually only published at regional scale (NUTS2)
- **I.14 Improving air quality:** based on manure management and fertilisation, but doesn't yet include the effect of ammonia absorption by tree foliage. Published only at national scale (NUTS 0)
- **I.15 Improving water quality** - reports separately for the potential threat of nitrate and phosphorus on arable land and groundwater. Reports separately for cropland, grassland and permanent crops, but again availability is at the NUTS 0 level, and not for all MS.
- **I.16 Water use in agriculture:** but the frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations vary from country to country, as does the number of sampling stations over the years. Published at river basin level.
- **I.17 Reducing pressure on water resources:** calculated for the Water Exploitation Index but only available at national level, or sometimes for river basins.

- **I.19 Increasing farmland bird populations.** Available at country (NUTS 0) level only. Most species will benefit from hedgerows and trees but other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) prefer open land - therefore a less integrated index is needed.
- **I.20 Percentage of species and habitats of Community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends:** but again, this is only available at NUTS 2/3 level and relates to broad habitat types
- **I.21 Agricultural land covered with landscape features:** but this is currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level based on LUCAS data from the JRC, or for woody landscape features based on Copernicus from the EEA

We make recommendation on which indicators, already reported for existing regulations, could be used for asserting the sustainability requirements of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation, so as to avoid creating new redundant indicators, and thus facilitate reporting and reducing the control effort for the administration. We consider that agroforestry can make a significant impact in all six areas of sustainability identified by the EU Sustainable Finance Initiative (aka the Taxonomy Regulation): climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, pollution, water resources, the circular economy, biodiversity and ecosystems.

Taking a farm in DigitAF's LL in Germany as a case study, we examined the possibility to compute these indicators at even finer scale: farm or field level. The results show promising possibilities using existing database for some indicators, but important bottlenecks in data availability/resolution for others. Therefore, we make several recommendations for improving data collection and provision: i) monitoring emissions at a parcel scale, ii) move to wall-to-wall identification of parcels and land use using the LPIS system and iii) increasing detail in parcel-level databases of soil information and woody vegetation levels, including in hedges, iv) harmonisation with methods used in CRCF certification.

Reporting Agri-Environmental Indicators (AEI) at field or farm scale, and giving access to the data to policy makers and practitioners (farmers) is the best way to allow them to quantify the effect of newly implemented agroforestry. Therefore, if we want to give farmers and policy makers the opportunity to actively evaluate their actions (direct feedback) and potentially reap benefits from agroforestry (carbon farming, biodiversity) as well as truly monitor the impact of environmental policies, the monitoring scale needs to be much finer than it currently is.

1 Introduction

1.1 DigitAF Project

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actors with tools to answer their needs, in particular digital tools. Three actors' groups are targeted by DigitAF:

- **Policy actors:** policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- **Practitioners:** farmers, landowners and extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AF and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm level and beyond.
- **Beneficiaries of AF products and services:** stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading carbon and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

When understanding the needs of these three actor groups with regard to agroforestry, the consortium works towards developing tailor-made digital tools that address the needs of each group.

1.2 About this report

This report was prepared as part of Work Package 1 "Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers". Its focus is on EU agri-environmental indicators and their transferability to province (NUTS3), municipality (NUTS4) or finer scales.

Task 1.4 of DigitAF aims to collect information on the inclusion of agroforestry systems in the existing CAP result, impact and EU agri-environmental indicators. Here, the issue of scale has proven to be crucial: so far, these indicators are solely reported at national or regional level (NUTS1/2), whereas agroforestry systems mainly have an impact on provincial, municipality and farm level (NUTS 3/4/5¹).

This report was developed in close collaboration with Work Package 4, T4.2 Data management and sharing and T4.3 DigitAF-Architecture: AF Software Community, Design and Environment by FAIRness score (Findable, Accessable, Interoperable and Re-usable). Thus, in this report, selected AEI datasets were also included in the data catalogue (T4.2) on the DigitAF website (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/>). These datasets are available to the whole project consortium and an interested public at any time.

The report begins with an overview of agri-environmental indicators selected as relevant to agroforestry systems on the basis of strong evidence. Data from these indicators data are then compared with the scientifically significant impacts (Chapter2). Selected indicators are assessed in terms of the availability of spatial data and the suitability of the data for field level analysis (Chapter 3). Building on the data collected, we mention ideas on how agri-environmental indicators could be collected and assessed in the future. The focus is on impacts at the local level caused by agroforestry and woody-landscape-features, as only these allow direct feedback to policy makers as well as practitioners (farmers/foresters) of the impact of specific measures. The report concludes with an overall assessment of agri-environmental indicators and their potential for monitoring agroforestry and landscape features (Chapter 4).

¹ NUTS 4 and 5 are now called Local Administrative Unit 1 and 2. Statistics and shapefiles are maintained by the EEA for LAU1. They are generally called "municipalities" in English, whereas NUTS3 are "counties" or "provinces".

2 Selection of Agri-Environmental Indicators

The increased emphasis on environmental issues in the European Union (European Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy, 'From Farm to Fork', CAP) requires farming practices to be more environmentally and climate-friendly (Dabkiene et al. 2021). The success of these policy objectives, and the measures defined to achieve them, are supposedly evaluated at regular intervals. This evaluation relies on agri-environmental indicators that have been defined to monitor the health of agroecosystems. However, the indicators lack consistency as each country, each (environmental) sector or each political measure has developed its own recording and evaluation methods. There are already several different indicator systems in the European Union alone. For example, EU Member States (MS) report on the results of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) using the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF, European Parliament 2021), while in the area of climate and environment they generally report using standardised agri-environmental indices (AEI) and state of ecosystem indices (MAES, Maes et al., 2012). Further standard data is collected in Farm Structure Survey (FSS, EUROSTAT 2024) and Farm Accounting Data Network (FADN). A Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) is in the process of implementation, but data will not be fully available until 2026 (European Parliament 2023).

This list shows that data is widely available but mostly reported only at Member State level (NUTS 1 or NUTS 2), and often consists of many different input data (with different spatial scales, from different data sources (modelling, surveys, etc.) or formats (tables, maps, etc.)). Data reported at a national scale (NUTS1) is of little help to local decision-makers or practitioners, even if they are very interested in it (Klaus et al. 2024). This is despite the fact that the measurements, calculations and reports are usually carried out at regional or provincial level (NUTS2-NUTS3) and should therefore be “easily” available.

With this in mind, the aim of this report is to identify environmental data that can be used at more localized levels (NUTS 4-5). This can be done by linking to open-source geodatabases or by using existing individual data reports (e.g., LPIS data). For example, data at farm scale is not only interesting and relevant as input for the carbon calculator (→ DigitAF WP1), but can also be useful for the assessment and monitoring of the European agri-environmental indicators (AEI). The identification and application of AEIs at different spatial scales (NUTS0, 1, 2, 3) is of paramount importance for assessing the extent and the impact of agroforestry systems.

A multi-stage approach was chosen to evaluate the environmental indicators with regard to their suitability for recording and evaluating agroforestry systems at the local level. This section therefore presents a systematic approach following the steps:

1. Selection of Agri-Environmental Indicators
 - a. Collection of agri-environmental indicators that are currently available, under discussion and/or to be introduced in the EU
 - b. Selection I: Indicators that show meaningful and sensitive effects for agroforestry (based on scientific studies)
2. Evaluation and application of agri-environmental indicators with regard to the impact assessment of agroforestry
 - a. collection of (spatial and thematic) data as well as monitoring methods covering the selected AEIs in the Member States
 - b. critical review of these data collection and reporting mechanisms in order to demonstrate the effects of agroforestry (e.g., at different spatial NUTS levels).

2.1 Collection and Selection of Agri-Environmental Indicators

For an initial selection of agri-environmental indicators, we have chosen all indicators for which individual studies have identified an effect. We focused on five legal frameworks: the European 8th Environment Action Programme, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Union Certification Framework for Permanent Carbon Removals, the Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience, and the Regulation on Nature Restoration.

2.1.1 EUROPEAN 8TH ENVIRONMENT ACTION PROGRAMME

In 2022, the EU published the Monitoring framework for the 8th Environment Action Programme: *Measuring progress towards the attainment of the Programme's 2030 and 2050 priority objectives COM(2022) 357 final* (European Commission 2022a). They mentioned 26 headline indicators for monitoring its environmental action programme. Each specific priority objective is monitored using two indicators, biodiversity alone is covered by three indicators.

The sub-targets are:

1. Climate change mitigation,
2. Climate change adaptation,
3. A regenerative circular economy,
4. Zero pollution and a toxic free environment,
5. Biodiversity and ecosystems,
6. Environmental and climate pressures related to EU production and consumption,
7. Enabling conditions,
8. Living well, within planetary boundaries

With regard to the performance of agroforestry, the following four indicators are directly related, while three others are of indirect importance. The complete list of indicators can be found in the appendix.

Table 1: AEI and their potential for monitoring agroforestry impacts under the 8th Environment Action Programme

Indicator Description	Remarks with regard to agroforestry
1. Climate change mitigation	
2. GHG emissions from land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF, tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent: Climate neutrality: increase net GHG removals by carbon sinks from the LULUCF sector to 310 million tonnes CO ₂ equivalent by 2030, based on data provided by EEA	Agroforestry is one of the carbon farming methodologies proposed for the EU in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework Woody vegetation is an important sink in national GHG Reporting (Kay et al. 2019; Lawson 2024).
2. Climate change adaptation	
3. Climate-related economic losses (in EUR billion): economic impact of climate change: reduce overall monetary losses from weather and climate-related events, data collected and provided by EEA	Agroforestry provides a modified microclimate (reduced wind speed, shade, reduced evapotranspiration) and thus mitigates extreme weather conditions to some extent. This can reduce yield variability. (Kanzler et al. 2019; Lawson et al. 2019, 2023)
4. Drought impact on ecosystems (area affected in km ²): Ecosystem resilience: decrease the area impacted by drought and loss of vegetation productivity	
Zero pollution / Water	

8. Nitrates in groundwater (mg of NO ₃ /l and % monitoring stations with value above 50 mg NO ₃ /l: clean water: reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% in safe groundwater resource, data collected and provided by EEA	Tree roots in agroforestry systems have the potential to reduce nitrogen (and phosphorus) residues in the soil, minimising the potential for leaching into groundwater (Pavlidis and Tsihrintzis 2018; Zhu et al. 2020)
Biodiversity	
10. Common bird index (index: 1990 = 100): Biodiversity preservation: reverse the decline in populations of common birds, data provided and collected by EBCC/ 32 BirdLife/ RSPB/CSO	Since some bird species benefit from trees and others do not, agroforestry is only partially positive for this indicator (Edo et al. 2023).
11. Forest connectivity (0-100 %): Healthy ecosystems: increase the degree of connectivity in forest ecosystems, with a view to creating and integrating ecological corridors and increase climate change resilience	For forest ecosystem connectivity, agroforestry can provide stepping stones and corridors (Lecq et al. 2017), but in some circumstances can lead to the spread of wildfires (Damianidis et al. 2021).
Environmental and climate pressures related to EU production and consumption	
13. Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption (in %): Sustainable energy: at least [45%] of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	Some agroforestry systems, such as short rotation coppice, are explicitly designed to produce agricultural biomass and renewable energies (Rockwood et al. 2004; Smith et al. 2012).
Living well, within planetary boundaries	
23. Water exploitation index plus (in %): Planetary boundaries/sustainable use of water: reduce water scarcity	Agroforestry reduces evapotranspiration of the crop / pasture and thus makes efficient use of available (rain) water (Kay et al. 2018; Jacobs et al. 2022)

2.1.2 COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY (CAP) 2023-2027

The *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)* regulates the support for European farmers. Therefore, the CAP 2023-2027 established 10 CAP specific objectives and evaluated them via the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) with a list of 44 Result indicators, 37 Output indicators and 49 Impact indicators (European Union 2021). The complete list of indicators can be found in the Appendix.

Assurance	Annual Performance Clearance <i>Linking expenditure to output</i>	Common OUTPUT Indicators 37 Indicators	1 indicator of interest for agroforestry
Monitoring	Performance Review <i>Checking progress towards targets</i>	Common RESULT indicators 44 Indicators	2 indicators of interest for agroforestry
Policy Performance	Evaluation activities <i>Assessing performance</i>	Common IMPACT indicators	14 indicators of interest for

	<i>towards objectives</i>	49 indicators	agroforestry
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Output Indicators

With regard to Assurance and annual performance clearance, only one output indicator is of interest for agroforestry. This is:

O.16 Number of hectares or number of other units under maintenance commitments for afforestation and agroforestry

The indicator shows the number of (forest) hectares or other units (such as trees) that are supported by **maintenance commitments** for afforestation and agroforestry.

➔ Shortcomings: The indicator includes both forest and agricultural land, which makes it difficult to separate the areas used for agroforestation and afforestation

A total of five member states have made interventions for O.16 on the topic of agroforestry within the EU Catalogue of Interventions (European Commission 2024). They refer to Specific Objective 4 (SP4) “Contributing to climate change mitigation”, SP5 “Efficient natural resource management” and SP6 “Halting and reversing biodiversity loss”. These are

- Belgium / Flanders: Maintenance of Agroforestry
- Czechia: Caring for an established agroforestry system
- Spain: Commitments to maintain afforestation and agroforestry systems (6502.2 IACS)
- Italy: Support for maintaining afforestation /afforestation and agroforestry systems
- Slovakia: Conservation and maintenance of plants under established agroforestry systems

However, a total of 21 interventions were attributed O.16. Some of these may be available for agroforestry, even if this is not explicitly mentioned in the title of the intervention. In Cyprus, for example, there is a measure titled "Maintenance of wooded areas", which could include agroforestry, but does not have to.

Result Indicators

With regard to Monitoring and Performance reviews, two of the result indicators relate to agroforestry. These are:

R.17PR: Afforested land: Area supported for afforestation, agroforestry and restoration, including breakdowns

This indicator mainly records the creation of forests and landscape elements on agricultural land through the planting of trees and/or hedges. It can potentially include some restoration of already planted forests - The reporting includes the initial investment costs, maintenance costs (Article 70) on a one-off basis and annual premiums for environmental schemes (Article 31), all on a per hectare basis. The reporting should be divided between: 1. Afforested area, 2. Restored area, 3. Agro-forestry area (The entire agroforestry area -both cultivated agricultural areas and areas under the planted landscape features), 4. Landscape features created (only areas of planted wooded landscape features)

➔ Shortcomings: The indicator focuses only on newly established agroforestry systems, which means that existing areas are not mentioned. In addition, newly established agroforestry systems can alternatively be included in “R.18 Investment support for the forest sector”, “R.16 Investments related to climate”, “R.26 Investments related to natural resources” and/or “R.32 Investments related to biodiversity”, or if the systems are established by beneficiaries other than farmers under “R.18 Investment support for the forest sector” and/or “R.27 Environmental or climate-related performance through investment in rural areas”.

R.34PR Preserving landscape features: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees

The indicator reports on the area (in % of the total UAA) that receives financial support for **the maintenance** of landscape features. Also, here maintenance costs (Article 70) and costs for environmental schemes (Article 31) are reported.

➔ Shortcomings: The restructuring and conversion of vineyards and the preservation/restoration of stone walls or terraces could also be included here. This means that the indicator not only covers agroforestry systems, but can also go beyond this.

Both indicators are subject to a performance review, i.e., they are monitored in 2025, 2026 and 2027 and compared towards the agreed targets. If the Member States do not achieve their targets (more than 25% deviation), they can be required to draw up an action plan, which must also be monitored in the subsequent period.

A total of eleven interventions (7 investment, 2 eco-schemes, 2 Environmental-Climates) were submitted for R.17. They refer to Specific Objective 1 (SP1) "Supporting viable farm income", SP4 "Contributing to climate change mitigation", SP5 "Efficient natural resource management", SP6 "Halting and reversing biodiversity loss" and SP8 "Jobs, growth and equality in rural areas". The interventions are:

- Austria: Non-productive arable land and agroforestry strips
- Czechia: Setting up an agroforestry system
- Greece: Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems rich in landscape elements
- Spain: Non-productive forest investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems
- Italy: Support for maintaining afforestation / afforestation and agroforestry systems
- Italy: Planting of afforestation / creation of woodland and agroforestry
- Poland: Establishment of agroforestry systems
- Portugal: Installation of agroforestry systems
- Portugal: Investment in the Creation and Regeneration of Agroforestry Systems
- Slovakia: Conservation and maintenance of plants under established agroforestry systems
- Slovakia: Establishment of an agroforestry system

Here too, a total of 72 interventions are counted for R17 and not every measure is clearly formulated. In Hungary, for example, there is a measure entitled "Support for investments in afforestation and the creation of woodland". Whether this includes agroforestry or not must be evaluated in the country-specific documents.

And for R34 a total of 66 interventions is listed, four of which are referring to agroforestry. They are mapped against Specific Purpose (SP4) "Contributing to climate change mitigation", SP5 "Efficient natural resource management" and SP6 "Halting and reversing biodiversity loss". The interventions are

- Austria: Non-productive arable land and agroforestry strips
- Czechia: Caring for an established agroforestry system
- Germany: Maintaining agroforestry practices on arable land and permanent grassland
- Greece: Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems rich in landscape elements
- Poland: Afforestation and woodland premiums and agroforestry systems

With R34, it is even more complicated to distinguish whether a measure includes agroforestry or not. In Croatia, for example, there is a measure called "Preservation of landscape features", in Estonia "Climate and Environment Plan: maintaining ecosystem services on arable land" or in Poland "Conservation of orchards of traditional varieties of fruit trees". In all these cases, the national documents would first have to be consulted in order to be able to say whether agroforestry is (also) addressed.

Context and Impact Indicators

Finally, when it comes to policy performance or evaluation of activities, ten impact and context indicators are of interest to agroforestry, or can be influenced by it. The impact indicators are also those in which farmers/landowners have a keen interest, as they take stock of what is happening on the ground (rather than evaluating monetary support as with the output and result indicators). The relevant indicators are:

Table 2: AEI and their potential for monitoring agroforestry impacts in the Context and Impact Indicators

Indicator Description	Remarks / Shortcomings with regard to agroforestry
<p>I.21 Agricultural land covered with landscape features The indicator reports on the area covered by landscape features in agricultural land such as hedges, trees, ponds, field margins, etc. Agroforestry trees and groups of trees are counted for landscape features.</p>	<p>The only information available is at NUTS3 level, either averaged from LUCAS data by the JRC or estimated for woody cover by the EEA (Lawson and De Boeck 2023).</p>
<p>I.20 Percentage of species and habitats of Community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends The indicator reports increasing and stable trends in i.) habitats and species of Community interest (Habitats Directive) and ii). pollinators. It only refers to habitats and species that are listed in the Annexes of the Habitats Directive and are associated with agroecosystems. The following are relevant for agroforestry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 6310 Dehesas with evergreen Quercus spp · 6530 Fennoscandian wooded meadows · 9070 Fennoscandian wooded pastures 	<p>The indicator refers exclusively to traditional agroforestry systems. Newly established systems and systems that are not listed in the Habitats Directive are not taken into account.</p>
<p>I.17 Reducing pressure on water resource For the "Water Exploitation Index PLUS (WEI+)" indicator, the estimated total water use is given as a percentage of renewable water flows (surface water and groundwater). The results are expressed as water use of the agricultural sector compared to other sectors (ii) or within the same sector over years (iii) at NUTS 0 level.</p>	<p>The reporting is only on NUTS0 level.</p>
<p>I.16 Reducing nutrient leakage The indicator is measured as nitrate concentrations in groundwater and rivers and expressed in mg NO₃/l for groundwater and mg N/l for rivers. The indicator is expressed as % of groundwater stations above the concentration threshold (50 mg NO₃/l)</p>	<p>The frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations vary from country to country, as does the number of sampling stations over the years. As a result, there is no continuous, spatially defined distribution of measuring points and the conclusions drawn vary depending on the sampling design/year.</p>
<p>I.13 Reducing soil erosion The indicator estimates</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. soil loss due to water erosion (t/ha/year) and II. the agricultural land with moderate to severe soil erosion risk (%). (Moderate i.e. 	<p>Soil losses due to gully erosion or wind erosion are not taken into account. The period between sampling and publication is at least 3 years. In addition, the reporting scale may (or may not) disregard agroforestry elements.</p>

<p>>5 t/ha/year to severe and severe i.e. >10 t/ha/year).</p>	
<p>I.11 Enhancing carbon sequestration The indicator models</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. the total organic carbon content in soils on agricultural land (with a breakdown by arable land, grassland and permanent crops) (= Mt of C), II. the mean organic carbon content in agricultural land (g of C/kg) and III. an estimate of SOC changes over time (=%). IV. It is based on the LUCAS soil survey. 	<p>Since agroforestry is included in all three categories (arable land, grassland and permanent crops), it is difficult to make a statement about the potential of agroforestry.</p>
<p>I.10 Contributing to climate change mitigation The indicator reports on</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. GHG emission from agriculture aggregating annual emissions of methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) from the following sources: enteric fermentation (CH₄); manure management (CH₄, N₂O); rice cultivation (CH₄); agricultural soil management (CH₄, N₂O, CO₂), including burning of field residues, liming and application of C-containing fertilisers. II. Share of GHG emissions from agriculture in total GHG emissions III. GHG emissions and removals from LULUCF IV. GHG emissions from agriculture including cropland and grassland: it represents the sum of GHG emissions from agriculture and GHG emissions and removals from LULUCF for cropland and grassland V. Share of GHG emissions from agriculture including cropland and grassland in total GHG emissions VI. GHG emissions from livestock: sum of enteric fermentation and manure management/ hectares of Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) VII. GHG emissions from ruminants: With regard to agroforestry, the iii. GHG Emissions and Removals from LULUCF are important 	<p>The carbon storage potential of agroforestry is reported in this indicator.</p>
<p>I.19 Increasing farmland bird populations The indicator reports on Bird population trends of 39 selected bird species that are common and characteristic of European farmland landscapes.</p>	<p>The reporting scale is NUTS0, which makes spatially clear trends (caused by agroforestry) impossible. In addition, among the 39 bird species monitored, there are some species that benefit from hedgerows and trees (e.g. hoopoe, common linnet, yellowhammer) and other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) that prefer open land and avoid wooded structures. Agroforestry can</p>

	therefore only be partially assessed as positive for this indicator.
<p>I.12 Increasing sustainable energy in agriculture</p> <p>The indicator presents the amount of renewable energy provided by agriculture and / or forestry. It is divided into</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. production of renewable energy from agricultural biomass (where available, energy crops for electricity or heat (including short rotation coppice) II. production of renewable energy from forestry biomass III. production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry IV. share of the combined production of renewable energy from agricultural and forestry biomass over the total primary energy production of renewable energy. 	Some agroforestry systems, such as short rotation coppice, are explicitly designed to produce agricultural biomass from the tree and shrub component of the agroforestry system.
<p>I.9 Improving the resilience of agriculture to climate change</p> <p>The indicator is built on several other (already mentioned) indicators. These are</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Agricultural factor income stability II. Crop production stability – annual cereals production resilience III. Water exploitation index plus (WEI+) regionally and monthly for the agricultural sector IV. Soil organic carbon in agricultural land 	While the first and second input indicators are not directly related to agroforestry, the third and fourth input indicators are directly influenced by agroforestry. Consequently, this should mean that more agroforestry should also lead to a more resilient agricultural system.
<p>I.14 Improving air quality</p> <p>This indicator reports the total annual ammonia emissions (NH₃) from agriculture (based on manure management and fertilization).</p>	The indicator only reports the emissions or emitters, i.e. it is “blind” to the benefits of agroforestry in binding ammonia from the soils and animals, and reducing indirect ammonia emission from water bodies with high nitrate levels
<p>I.15 Improving water quality</p> <p>The indicator illustrates the potential threat caused by nitrate and phosphorus loss into groundwater. It is modelled based on arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland and mainly includes the consumption of mineral fertilisers and seeding and plant material, livestock population and manure import and exports, use of other organic fertilisers in agricultural production, atmospheric deposition, biological nitrogen fixation, crop and fodder production and crop/fodder residues removal or burning, and areas of various types of crops.</p>	The indicator reports on potential nitrate and phosphorus pollution based on the three categories "arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland". Agroforestry systems are not yet included as an option. This means that neither positive nor negative effects can be reported if agroforestry is introduced.

<p>I.18 Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides</p> <p>The indicator focuses on the risk, use and impact of pesticides and consists of three sub-indicators:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Sales of pesticides II. The Harmonised Risk based on the sales of pesticides (Indicator 1) III. Sales of more hazardous pesticides 	<p>The indicator focuses only on the level of pesticide sales, i.e., the benefits of agroforestry in terms of reduced pesticide use cannot be clearly attributed to this indicator.</p>
<p>Land cover</p> <p>The indicator measures the area in the different categories of land cover and it consists of 6 specific indicators:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Artificial surface, 2. Agricultural areas, 3. Natural grassland, 4. Forest, 5. Transitional woodland-shrub, 6. Wetlands and water bodies 	<p>Agroforestry and landscape-features are not listed as a separate category, i.e., these areas can be found in 2. agricultural areas, in 3. natural grassland and in 5. transitional woodland-shrub</p>

Agroforestry practitioners see the all-encompassing impact of agroforestry. But the indicators above relevant to agroforestry relate only to three CAP specific objectives (see figure 1): “Climate change”, “environmental care” and “landscapes”. Only one indicator (R17) relates to “fair income”, and to “rural areas”. In view of the great potential of agroforestry systems, this is a major shortcoming, as it completely ignores other fields of action. Agroforestry could make a major contribution, particularly in the areas of rural areas, food and health or fair income.

Figure 1: CAP Specific Objectives related to the Impact Indicators relevant for agroforestry

2.1.3 REGULATION ON NATURE RESTORATION AND AMENDING REGULATION

On 17 June 2024, the Nature Restoration Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament was published and entered into force on August 18th. The regulation sets legally binding targets for the restoration of degraded ecosystems. The following indicators are to be used to monitor the fulfilment of the objectives of the legislation.

Table 3: AEI and their potential for monitoring agroforestry impacts in the Nature Restoration Regulation – agricultural landscapes

Indicator Description	Remarks / Shortcomings with regard to agroforestry
Agricultural Landscapes	
Member States should monitor, and ensure an increasing trend until a “satisfactory” level is achieved for two out of the following three	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> grassland butterfly index 	This indicator can only be used in agroforestry systems with grassland. It says more about the quality of the grassland than about the agroforestry system.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stock of organic carbon in cropland mineral soils 	See also Table 2, I 11 Since agroforestry is included in all three categories (arable land, grassland and permanent crops), it is difficult to make a statement about the potential of agroforestry.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features 	See also Table 2, I21. The only information available is at NUTS3 level (Lawson and De Boeck 2023).
They should also monitor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the common farmland bird index 	See also Table 2, I19 The reporting scale is NUTS0, which makes spatially clear trends (caused by agroforestry) impossible. In addition, among the 39 bird species monitored, there are some species that benefit from hedgerows and trees (e.g. hoopoe, common linnet, yellowhammer) and other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) that prefer open land and avoid wooded structures. Agroforestry can therefore only be partially assessed as positive for this indicator.
Restore organic soils / restoring drained peatlands under agricultural use	
Forest Landscapes	
MS should monitor and ensure an increasing trend until “satisfactory levels” are reached	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> standing deadwood; lying deadwood; 	Dead wood, standing or lying, could also be reported in agroforestry systems.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • share of forests with uneven-aged structure 	The uneven aged structure could be extended on agroforestry systems
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • forest connectivity 	Also, this indicator could include agroforestry systems
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stock of organic carbon 	It would be beneficial to report not only the SOC of forests, but also of agroforestry. See also Table 2, I 11

2.1.4 PROPOSAL FOR A DIRECTIVE ON SOIL MONITORING AND RESILIENCE

In July 2023, the EU presented a ‘Proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law)’ (European Commission 2023). Following the involvement of Member States and stakeholders, the list of indicators to be monitored was drawn up as follows (European Parliament 2024). With the exception of “salinisation” and “soil contamination”, these indicators can also be (positively) influenced by agroforestry:

Table 4: AEI and their potential for monitoring agroforestry impacts under the Proposal for Soil Monitoring and Resilience

Degradation factors	Soil descriptors	Remarks / Shortcomings with regard to agroforestry
Soil erosion	Soil erosion rate (tonnes of loss soil per hectare per year)	Agroforestry can prevent soil erosion (Durán Zuazo and Rodríguez Pleguezuelo 2008; JRC 2024).
Loss of soil organic carbon	Soil organic carbon concentration (g per kg)	Agroforestry can increase the soil organic carbon concentration (Cardinael et al. 2017; JRC 2024)
Soil compaction	Bulk density in topsoils (g cm ⁻³)	Tree roots can loosen the soil and therefore reduce compaction in the long term.
Excess nutrient content in soil	Available phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹); total nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹)	Tree roots in agroforestry systems have the potential to reduce nitrogen (and phosphorus) residues in the soil, minimising the potential for leaching into groundwater (Pavlidis and Tsihrintzis 2018; Zhu et al. 2020)
Reduction of soil capacity to retain water	Water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of volume of water); volume of saturated soil	Tree roots have the potential to retain water in the soil (Jacobs et al. 2022; JRC 2024).
Soil ecological functions		
Soil aggregation	Water-stable aggregates (%)	Little is known about the impact of agroforestry on this indicator.
Soil respiration	Soil microbial basal respiration (µl O ₂)	Little is known about the impact of

	$\text{h}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$ soil dry weight)	agroforestry on this indicator.
Soil biomass	Soil microbial biomass carbon (Cmic $\mu\text{g Cg}^{-1}$ soil dry weight)	Little is known about the impact of agroforestry on this indicator.
Soil biodiversity		
Taxonomic diversity	Diversity of soil organisms through (presence counts per taxonomic group based on metabarcoding)	Little is known about the impact of agroforestry on this indicator.
Population abundance	Total abundances of bacteria and archaea; total abundances of fungi; total number and proportion of pathogenic fungi; total nematode abundance per functional group based on morphology	Little is known about the impact of agroforestry on this indicator.
Soil habitat		
Soil structure	Size class proportions (sand, silt, clay); proportion of coarse materials (>2mm)	This indicator is neither positively nor negatively influenced by agroforestry, but reflects the local situation.

2.1.5 EU CARBON REMOVALS AND CARBON FARMING CERTIFICATION (CRCF) REGULATION

The European Commission published the **Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products (COM/2022/672 final)** (European Commission 2022b). This defines and regulates carbon farming in agriculture and carbon storage in products. In addition to pure carbon storage, the systems to be certified shall also meet the requirements of Article 7 Sustainability. It says:

Article 7

1. An activity shall not significantly harm and may generate co-benefits for one or more of the following sustainability objectives:

(a) climate change mitigation beyond the net carbon removal benefit and net soil emission reduction benefit referred to in Article 4(1) and (1a);

(b) climate change adaptation;

(c) sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources;

(d) transition to a circular economy, including the efficient use of sustainably sourced bio-based materials;

(e) pollution prevention and control;

(f) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems including soil health, as well as avoidance of land degradation.

(fa) 1a. A carbon farming activity shall at least generate co-benefits for the sustainability objective referred to in point (f) of this paragraph

Agroforestry is a candidate for a carbon removal activity and must therefore fulfil the above-mentioned sustainability criteria. In order to use existing evaluation structures as well as collected data and thus create synergies and avoid additional work, we examine below to what extent the CAP performance indicators (PMEF indicators) as well as the headline indicators that have already been collected can also be used for these sustainability requirements. Using already existing indicators and reporting structures can make the reporting effort easier for those interested in carbon removal activities, as well as reducing the control effort for the administration.

3 Application of Agri-environmental indicators at farm level

3.1 Spatial data on Agri-environmental indicators

Six indicators were selected to be analysed in more detail with regard to their data availability in existing and established EU databases. It can be seen that very different reporting levels exist or that some of the AEI are not recorded at all.

Table 5: Selected agri-environmental indicators (AEI), their reporting level, input data (Eurostat database) and responsible institution

Agroforestry impacts meta-analysis	Required Data	Spatial resolution
GHG Emissions	EEA GHG Emission Data	NUTS 0
Biodiversity	European Bird Census Council (EBCC); Pan-European Common Bird Monitoring Scheme (PECBMS)	NUTS 0 Variable survey plots (Best Practice Guide)
Soil Erosion	Soil erosion by water (RUSLE2015)	100 x 100 m
Carbon Sequestration	Soil Organic Matter (SOM) fractions	1 x 1 km
Soil Nutrients	LUCAS topsoil database	Point data to 250 x 250 m (Gaussian Process Regression)
Soil Water Retention	Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe	1 x 1 km

This report was developed in close collaboration with Work Package 4, T4.2 Data management and sharing and T4.3 DigitAF-Architecture: AF Software Community, Design and Environment by FAIRness. The indicators selected in this report were also included in the data catalogue (T4.2) on the DigitAF website (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/>).

3.2 The German Case Study

The following chapter focuses on the applicability of agri-environmental indicators at farm and field level, using the example of an agroforestry farm in the DigitAF Living Lab in Germany. The farm is about 300 ha, the agroforestry field is about 7 ha (Figure 2, Table 6).

Table 6: Spatial Scale (NUTS level) for the Living Lab Farm in Germany

Spatial Scale / NUTS Level	Name	Area (ha)
NUTS 0	Germany	35 800 000
NUTS 1	Brandenburg	2 900 000
NUTS 2	Brandenburg	2 900 000
NUTS 3	Oberspreewald-Lausitz, DE40B	122 300
Field	Agroforestry Plot, DigitAF LL	7

Figure 2: Spatial allocation of the farm within NUTS 0, 1, 2, 3

In the context of agroforestry, identifying and applying indicators that can efficiently use data at the farm level is of foremost importance. We looked for suitable monitoring approaches with a correspondingly high geospatial resolution for these impact categories. In the following paragraphs, we will highlight the potential of using field-level data to calculate each AEIs.

3.2.1 GHG EMISSIONS

Indicator	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture Share of agriculture in GHG emissions
Unit	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture: (ktonnes CO ₂ equivalents/yr)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European 8th Environment Action Programme, Headline Indicator: 2. GHG emissions from land use, land use change and forestry • Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027, Impact Indicator: I.10 Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture
Scale	NUTS 0 (Country scale) Data https://dqiataf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/data/dataset/emissions_report_unfccc
Background	Carbon dioxide (CO ₂), methane (CH ₄) and nitrous oxide (N ₂ O) are the greenhouse gases accounted for. CH ₄ and N ₂ O in particular are produced in agriculture through enteric fermentation in animal husbandry or through manure or fertiliser management.
Assessment method and databases	The IPCC methodology is standardised, transparent and applied in all Member States, so that it is comparable within and between EU Member States (with the exception of national values for animal excreta). However, different assessment quality levels (Tier1,2,3) are still applied in Europe. The following GHG are included as total amounts of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon dioxide (in kg CO₂ / ha /yr); • Methane (in kg CH₄ / ha /yr, or kg CO₂-equivalents / ha /yr ; and

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrous oxide (in kg N₂O-N / ha /yr or kg CO₂-equivalents / ha /yr)
Benefits of Agroforestry	The only synthesis paper available shows a positive effect of agroforestry on the reduction of greenhouse emissions at a global scale (JRC 2024).
German case study performance	<p>In 2023, emissions from Germany's agricultural sector are ~60 million tonnes of CO₂ eq. The German LULUCF sector has decrease from net storage of 32.8 million tonnes of CO₂eq in 1990 to 3.6 million tonnes of CO₂eq in 2023 (Umweltbundesamt 2023).</p> <p>In comparison, the LL farm established 7 ha of agroforestry with about 1 ha of tree strips. This results in carbon storage of ~10 t CO₂eq per year.</p>
Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	<p>Greenhouse gas fluxes are difficult to assess at a small spatial level. Therefore, the reporting level is usually for the country. Germany keeps a 100 x 100m matrix of land use and calculates fluxes for grassland, cropland, forest land separately. The challenge is that not many countries are reporting the impact of woody vegetation on grassland</p> <p>The Climate Law and the LULUCF Regulation expect MS to move to Tier 3 reporting for major GHG emission pools and a wall-to-wall identification of land parcels. The German Land Use Matrix currently uses 100m pixels but does not yet monitor emissions at a parcel scale or the impact of woody vegetation on grassland. However, it is being continuously improved. See also EURAF Policy Briefing #15 (v4) (Lawson and Muraru 2024) and #17 (v4)(Lawson 2024).</p> <p>Potential direct feedback to farmers on their farm's GHG emissions and management practices would have the potential to firstly raise awareness of GHG-relevant management and secondly actively reduce GHG emissions in agriculture.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential for Carbon Calculator (→DigitAF WP1) on farm and landscape level Move to wall-to-wall identification of parcels and land use using the LPIS system and increasing detail in parcel-level databases of soil information and woody vegetation levels, including in hedges. Harmonisation with methods used in CRCF certification (LULUCF)

3.2.2 FARMLAND BIRD INDEX

Indicator	Farmland bird population index
Unit	Bird population trends of selected bird species that are common and characteristic of European farmland landscapes.
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European 8th Environment Action Programme - Headline Indicators: 10. Common bird index Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027 Impact Indicators: I.19 Farmland Bird Index Nature Restoration Regulation: Common farmland bird index
Scale	<p>NUTS 0 (Country scale)</p> <p>Data: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/data/dataset/common_bird_monitoring_schemes</p>
Background	Biodiversity loss due to agricultural practices remains one of the most pressing environmental problems in the EU, especially as almost 50% of the EU's land area is

	<p>used for agriculture. A large proportion of the species and habitats that are protected in Europe are found in these agricultural areas.</p> <p>Farmland birds are a good indicator of changes in the state of biodiversity (Reif et al. 2024). According to Triquet et al. (2024), birds are the most commonly used indicator species group to assess the effectiveness of AE schemes at the landscape scale.</p>																																																																																																								
Assessment method and databases	Pan-European Common Bird Monitoring Scheme (PECBMS): Field monitoring by local experts, several methods have been validated and in place for several years. E.g. for Germany (Kamp et al. 2021)																																																																																																								
Benefits of Agroforestry	Out of the 11 synthesis papers (focussed on global, African, Asian, South American, only 2 on European level), 6 show positive effect of agroforestry on biodiversity. Seven synthesis papers report a negative effect compared to intact forests. Two synthesis papers report no impact on bird abundance compared to intact forest at the global scale. Only EU-Study: AF Positive effect, compared to all land uses (JRC 2024).																																																																																																								
German case study performance	<p>Current data is available on NUTSO (country level) as an excel table in a national report (BFN et al. 2020)</p> <p>Bird species benefiting from agroforestry</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Deutscher Name</th> <th rowspan="2">Wissenschaftlicher Name</th> <th rowspan="2">Status</th> <th colspan="4">Bestandsituation bundesweit</th> <th colspan="3">Bestandsituation in SPA</th> <th colspan="3">Verbreitung</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Bestand 2011-2016</th> <th>Einheit</th> <th>Trend Lang</th> <th>Trend 36 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 24 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> <th>Bestand 2011-2016</th> <th>Bestandsanteil [%]</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 36 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Bluthänfling</td> <td><i>Linaria cannabina</i></td> <td>I</td> <td>110 000-205 000</td> <td>Rev.</td> <td>(c)</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Wiedehopf</td> <td><i>Upupa epops</i></td> <td>I</td> <td>800-950</td> <td>Rev.</td> <td>(c)</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>550-650</td> <td>69</td> <td></td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Bird species not benefiting from agroforestry</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Deutscher Name</th> <th rowspan="2">Wissenschaftlicher Name</th> <th rowspan="2">Status</th> <th colspan="4">Bestandsituation bundesweit</th> <th colspan="3">Bestandsituation in SPA</th> <th colspan="3">Verbreitung</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Bestand 2011-2016</th> <th>Einheit</th> <th>Trend Lang</th> <th>Trend 36 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 24 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> <th>Bestand 2011-2016</th> <th>Bestandsanteil [%]</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 36 Jahre</th> <th>Trend 12 Jahre</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Kiebitz</td> <td><i>Vanellus vanellus</i></td> <td>I</td> <td>42 000-67 000</td> <td>Pa.</td> <td>(c)</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>19 000-20 000</td> <td>37</td> <td></td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Feldlerche</td> <td><i>Alauda arvensis</i></td> <td>I</td> <td>1,2-1,85 Mio.</td> <td>Rev.</td> <td>(c)</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>↔</td> <td>↔</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Deutscher Name	Wissenschaftlicher Name	Status	Bestandsituation bundesweit				Bestandsituation in SPA			Verbreitung			Bestand 2011-2016	Einheit	Trend Lang	Trend 36 Jahre	Trend 24 Jahre	Trend 12 Jahre	Bestand 2011-2016	Bestandsanteil [%]	Trend 12 Jahre	Trend 36 Jahre	Trend 12 Jahre	Bluthänfling	<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	I	110 000-205 000	Rev.	(c)	↔	↔	↔				↔	↔	Wiedehopf	<i>Upupa epops</i>	I	800-950	Rev.	(c)	↔	↔	↔	550-650	69		↔	↔	Deutscher Name	Wissenschaftlicher Name	Status	Bestandsituation bundesweit				Bestandsituation in SPA			Verbreitung			Bestand 2011-2016	Einheit	Trend Lang	Trend 36 Jahre	Trend 24 Jahre	Trend 12 Jahre	Bestand 2011-2016	Bestandsanteil [%]	Trend 12 Jahre	Trend 36 Jahre	Trend 12 Jahre	Kiebitz	<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	I	42 000-67 000	Pa.	(c)	↔	↔	↔	19 000-20 000	37		↔	↔	Feldlerche	<i>Alauda arvensis</i>	I	1,2-1,85 Mio.	Rev.	(c)	↔	↔	↔				↔	↔
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Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	As the data is currently only reported at country level, it does not allow for feedback on the impact of specific land use or (field) management on the indicators.																																																																																																								
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some of the data is available at a smaller scale in the MS, but is summarised at country level. A spatial visualisation of the results would be desirable. A discussion on the extension of biodiversity indicators to butterflies / pollination / pest control could also be useful for monitoring agroforestry 																																																																																																								

3.2.3 SOIL EROSION BY WATER

Indicator	Areas with a certain level of erosion risk
Unit	Estimated soil loss by water erosion (t/ha/year)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027, Impact Indicators: I.13 Soil erosion by water Proposal on a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience: Soil erosion
Scale	100x100m (Last update 2015), Data https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/data/dataset/soilerosionbywater
Background	<p>Soil erosion, the removal of soil by predominantly water, leads to a deterioration in soil quality. It is highly dependent on the local geomorphology, soil type, land use, cultural practices and climate.</p> <p>The eroded soil material can also lead to sedimentation of reservoirs and riverbeds, flooding, water pollution and costly damage to infrastructure.</p>

Assessment method and databases	<p>Calculated / modelled Revised Universal soil loss Equation (RUSLE) based on: (Panagos et al. 2015)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil data: texture, organic carbon content, structure, permeability, • Climate data: precipitation (high temporal resolution), temperature • Land cover: as provided from LUCAS with land cover data from CORINE • Topography: as provided by e.g. the topographic model Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) • Management: human and agricultural practices
Benefits of Agroforestry	<p>Out of the 4 synthesis papers dealing with this type of impact, 3 show positive effect of agroforestry on soil erosion control: 2 compared to land use without trees (cropland) in Sub-Saharan Africa and Tropical zones, and one compared to forests in Europe (JRC 2024).</p>
German case study performance	<p>The field covers 4-6 grid cells. Therefore, the establishment of agroforestry will lead to changes in erosion assessment and AEI (provided that the associated land use and management changes are reflected in the input data).</p>
Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	<p>Soil, climate and topography data are either difficult to collect (soil) or can also be important on a larger scale (climate). However, this is not the case for land cover and management data which is available in the LPIS at plot level and should therefore be used for this AEI.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculations based on LPIS data for Land cover and management

3.2.4 CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Indicator	Carbon Sequestration
Unit	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) concentration (g per kg)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027, Impact Indicators: I.11 Soil organic carbon in agricultural land • Regulation on Nature Restoration and Amending Regulation: Stock of organic carbon in cropland mineral soils • Proposal on a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience: Loss of soil organic carbon
Scale	<p>1 x 1 km</p> <p>Data: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/data/dataset/som_fractions</p>
Background	<p>Soil organic matter is used as an indicator of soil health, but it is also used to measure the potential of soils to store carbon and thus mitigate climate change. The aim is to increase (or maintain) the SOC content over the years.</p> <p>Soil monitoring proposal criteria for healthy soil condition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For organic soils: respect targets set for such soils at national level in accordance with Article 4.1, 4.2, 9.4 of Regulation (EU)

	- For mineral soils: SOC/Clay ratio > 1/13;
Assessment method and databases	Soil monitoring proposal: ISO 10694:1995 Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion For the Soil Organic Matter (SOM) fractions map: Based on the LUCAS point data from 2009 (352 samples for all land uses and 186 samples only for grassland and forest), the SOM fractions are upscaled and modelled using land cover and a machine learning approach (Lugato et al. 2021).
Benefits for Agroforestry	Out of the 13 synthesis papers dealing with this type of impact, 10 show positive effect of agroforestry on carbon sequestration compared to land use without trees (including cropland and pastureland) at the global scale, in Europe and in other continents (JRC 2024).
German case study performance	The 7-ha field covers plots are 3 different raster cells. In practice, this means that long-term changes resulting from the introduction of agroforestry should be visible. In the short term, however, no changes will be measurable, as the measured values represent an average of approximately 2.3 ha (7 ha / 3 grid cells).
Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	SOC levels should increase over time. Therefore, regular measurements or time series should be carried out on each field.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Member States are obliged to make national implementations of the Farm Sustainability Tool for nutrients (FaST) available to farmers by the end of 2024. This is a parcel-by-parcel database of soil conditions and nutrient practices. • In Switzerland, farmers are obliged to carry out soil tests on their fields every 10 years in order to receive direct payments.

3.2.5 SOIL NUTRIENTS

Indicator	Soil Nutrients
Unit	Available phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹) Total nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposal on a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience: Excess nutrient content in soil – limits by MS
Scale	LUCAS topsoil database, point database (around 20.000 samples across Europe)
Background	Healthy soils are in good chemical, biological and physical condition. Improving water retention and nutrient availability in soils, soil structure, soil biodiversity and carbon sequestration increases the resilience of ecosystems, including agricultural production.

Assessment method and databases	<p>Soil monitoring proposal:</p> <p><i>Available phosphorus (mg kg⁻¹)</i> based on ISO 11263:1994 for spectrometric determination of phosphorus soluble in sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (P-Olsen)</p> <p>Potential criteria for healthy soil condition: Smaller as “maximum value”, the “maximum value” shall be laid down by the Member State within the range 30-50 mg kg⁻¹</p> <p><i>Total nitrogen in soil (mg g⁻¹)</i> based on ISO 11261:1995 for determination of total soil nitrogen using a modified Kjeldahl method</p>
Benefits of Agroforestry	<p>Out of the 7 synthesis papers, 5 show positive effect of agroforestry on soil nutrients: 4 comparing agroforestry to land use without trees (cropland and pastureland) at the global scale (mainly in Arid and Tropical zones), and one comparing it to forests in Europe. Three synthesis papers report an uncertain effect: two in West Africa (one compared to cropland and one unspecified) and one in Europe (compared to cropland and pastureland) (JRC 2024).</p>
Example Case study German	<p>There is a single point within NUTS 3 DE40B in more or less close proximity to the agroforestry field in Germany.</p> <p>That means that positive (or negative) changes in nutrient content in soil due to the 7-ha agroforestry field cannot be detected with this monitoring approach and are therefore not reflected in the national monitoring.</p>
Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	<p>Regular soil measurements or time series are very time consuming and costly.</p>
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member States are obliged to make national implementations of the Farm Sustainability Tool for nutrients (FaST) available to farmers by the end of 2024. This is a parcel-by-parcel database of soil conditions and nutrient practices.

3.2.6 SOIL WATER RETENTION

Indicator	Soil Water Retention
Unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Field: Soil water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of volume of water / volume of saturated soil) Map: Water retention of topsoil: saturated water content (cm³/cm³), water content at field capacity (cm³/cm³), water content at wilting point (cm³/cm³)
Indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposal on a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience: Reduction of soil capacity to retain water
Scale	<p>1000x1000m - Soil hydraulic properties maps (2016) for Europe</p> <p>Data: https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/maps-indicators-soil-hydraulic-properties-europe</p>

Background	<p>Healthy soils are in good chemical, biological and physical condition. Improving water retention and nutrient availability in soils, soil structure, soil biodiversity and carbon sequestration increases the resilience of ecosystems, including agricultural production.</p> <p>Use was made of the European Soil Database that contains information based on expert knowledge at the scale of the Soil Typological Unit (STU) and the Soil Mapping Unit (SMU)</p>
Assessment method and databases	<p>Field Method: Methodology to determine the value for one sample point: Option 1: LABORATORY: ISO 11274:2019 for determination of the water-retention characteristic. // Option 2: ESTIMATION: apply methodology (Tóth et al. 2015). (Soil Monitoring Proposal)</p> <p>Map method: European Soil Database that contains information based on expert knowledge at the scale of the Soil Typological Unit (STU) and the Soil Mapping Unit (SMU) (Tóth et al. 2015).</p>
Benefits of Agroforestry	<p>Out of the 7 synthesis papers, 6 show positive effect of agroforestry on water retention: 5 compared to land use without trees (cropland) at the global scale (mainly in Tropical zones in Africa and Asia), and one compared to forest plantations in China. Two synthesis papers report an uncertain effect in West Africa (one compared to cropland and one unspecified). One synthesis paper reported no effect compared to different types of forest in the control (e.g., plantations, unmanaged forests) (JRC 2024).</p>
Example German Case study	<p>Map: The monitoring units of 1000x1000m, i.e. 3 grid cells, cover the agroforestry area. This means that if a new area were to be established, a rather small impact would be detected with this indicator at this time.</p>
Critical reflections / Bottlenecks	<p>Regular soil retentions measurements or time series are very time consuming and costly.</p>
Recommendations	

4 Evaluation of Agri-Environmental Indicators

Table 7 shows a synthesis of the evaluation of all previously mentioned Agri-Environmental indicators, in terms of relevance for agroforestry, capacity to capture the effect of agroforestry, reporting level and as potential indicators for the carbon certification regulation.

Table 7: List of all agri-environmental indicators relevant to agroforestry - the indicators highlighted in green have shown significant importance in scientific paper (importance is reported as arbitrary units going from 0 - not important, to 5, very important). The potential for certification links the indicator to the category of the certification (a: climate change mitigation; (b) climate change adaptation; (c) sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources; (d) transition to a circular economy, (e) pollution prevention and control; (f) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems including soil health, as well as avoidance of land degradation.)

Agri-Environmental Indicators	Source	Category	AF Relevance	Scientific Evidence	Indicators Capacity to capture AF impacts	Reporting level	Potential for Certificates
2. GHG emissions from land use, land use change and forestry	<i>EU 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP)</i>	<i>Climate change mitigation (CCM)</i>	5	5	0	NUTS 0	(a)
I.10 Contributing to climate change mitigation (GHG Emissions)	<i>CAP Impact Indicators</i>	<i>CCM</i>	5	5	0	NUTS 0	(a)
I.9 Agricultural sector resilience progress indicator	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Climate change adaptation (CCA)</i>	2	Calculated indicator, based on a number of individual indicators	2	NUTS 0	(b)
3. Climate-related economic losses	<i>EAP</i>	<i>CCA</i>	2	3	0	NUTS 0	(b)
4. Drought impact on ecosystems	<i>EAP</i>	<i>CCA</i>	3	3	0	NUTS 0	(b)
I.16 Reducing nutrient leakage	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Zero pollution</i>	5	4	1		(e)
8. Nitrates in groundwater	<i>EAP</i>	<i>Zero pollution</i>	5	4	1		(e);
Soil contamination	<i>Proposal Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (PSoild)</i>	<i>Zero pollution</i>	1	1	0		(e)
Salinization	<i>PSoild</i>	<i>Zero pollution</i>	1	1	0		(e)
I.19 Farmland Bird Index	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	3	3	0	NUTS 0	(f)
10. Common bird index	<i>EAP</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	3	3	0	NUTS 0	(f)

Common farmland bird index	<i>Nature Restoration and Amending Regulation (NRR)</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	3	3	0	NUTS 0	(f)
I.21 Agricultural land covered with landscape features	<i>CAP Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Biodiversity and ecosystems</i>	5	Report on area size only	5	NUTS 0	(f)
Share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features	<i>NRR</i>	<i>Biodiversity and ecosystems</i>	5	Report on area size only			(f)
I.20 Percentage of species and habitats of Community interest	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Biodiversity and ecosystems</i>	5	Report on area size only	5	NUTS 0	(f)
11. Forest connectivity	<i>EAP</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	4				(f)
Forest connectivity	<i>NRR</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	4				(f)
Grassland butterfly index;	<i>NRR</i>	<i>Biodiversity</i>	2	1			(f)
I.11 Enhancing carbon sequestration	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	4	4	1		(f)
Stock of organic carbon in cropland mineral soils	<i>NRR</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	4	4	1		(f)
Loss of soil organic carbon	<i>PSoilD</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	4	4	1		(f)
I.13 Soil erosion by water	<i>Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	5	5	4		(f)
Soil erosion	<i>PSoilD</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	5	5	4		(f)
I.12 Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry	<i>CAP Impact Indicators</i>	<i>EU production and consumption</i>	3	1	3		
13. Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	<i>EAP</i>	<i>EU production and consumption</i>	2	0		NUTS 0	
I.17 Reducing pressure on water resources	<i>CAP Impact Indicators</i>	<i>Living well, within planetary boundaries</i>	4	3	0	NUTS 0	(c)
23. Water exploitation index plus	<i>EAP</i>	<i>Living well, within planetary boundaries</i>	3	3	1		(c)
Excess nutrient content in soil – limits by MS	<i>PSoilD</i>	<i>Natural Ressources</i>	4	3	2		(f)

Overall, there are several agro-environmental indicators that could report on the impacts of agroforestry. However, there are two types of limitation

- On the one hand, there are impacts that show significant positive effects (pollination, pest control) that are not captured by the indicators.
- On the other hand, agroforestry is not covered at an appropriate scale by existing indicators, as it is insufficiently addressed or included, and in some cases not at all. This does not meet the needs of practitioners or policy makers.

It is therefore difficult to use existing indicators as a basis for the sustainability criteria in the CRCF Regulation, although the existing proposal currently mentions NRR indicators.

Greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration, as well as soil erosion and soil water retention, would be promising indicators of agroforestry impacts. However, indicators that measure impacts on water quality and biodiversity are more difficult to measure in practice, and the various, sometimes overlapping, environmental impacts are difficult to separate.

In this report, we have presented some ideas for spatially differentiated methods that also include the (sometimes very small) agroforestry fields, landscape features or field boundaries and thus integrate their effects into environmental monitoring. For agri-environmental indicators in Europe, these small-scale evaluation and monitoring methods do not yet exist. However, there is an urgent need to further develop reporting systems down to the field level in order to make these small efforts for ecological improvement visible in reporting and thus also to appreciate them. The DigitAF project is developing tools for farmers, policy makers and beneficiaries and will seek to integrate these environmental impacts into the tools, while further simplifying and automating reporting for farmers, thus establishing a direct link to the policy level of regions, member states and the EU.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

Building on the regional data collected in this report, we present some innovative ideas on what and how agri-environmental indicators could be collected and assessed in the future, with a particular focus on the local impacts of agroforestry and woody-landscape-features, as these are the only ones that allow direct feedback to policy makers and practitioners (farmers) on the measures implemented.

As shown, Member States evaluate the AEI mostly at country (NUTS 0,1) and partly at regional or provincial level (NUTS 2-NUTS 3). This does not allow the effect of newly implemented agroforestry to be seen. However, if we want to give farmers and policy makers the opportunity to actively evaluate their actions (direct feedback) and potentially reap benefits from agroforestry (carbon farming, biodiversity) as well as truly monitor the impact of environmental policies, the monitoring level needs to be scaled down. Some initial starting points for such improvement are identified in this report.

In a next step, DIGITAF will develop protocols for farmers and policy makers.

- a. Protocols for the integration and storage of small-scale environmental data at the level of municipalities (NUTS4), farms or parcels (LPIS). This information could be linked to a national or regional open-source geodatabase such as the JRC-FaST platform, the DigitAF OpenFarmCarbonTracker or the CRCF Carbon Farming Registry -both of which operate at a parcel scale. DitiAf is also developing a Regional Knowledge Hub and Tool and Data catalogue.
➔ **Standardized protocol for storing farm-level data for standard agri-environmental indices (AEI) ➔ Link to CARBON Calculator (WP1.5)**
- b. Protocol to hold farm-scale data needed to operate the OpenFarmCarbonTracker, including the location and density of trees. Testing the protocol to collect relevant Living Lab data and use it to run the updated Carbon Calculator.

➔ **Testing protocols and data integration into the Link to CARBON Calculator (WP1.5) and Living Lab work (WP4)**

6 Acknowledgements

The DigitAF project (Grant Agreement N° 101059794) is co-funded by the European Commission, European Research Agency, within the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 6: “Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment”. The views and opinions expressed in this report are purely those of the writers and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

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8 Annex

Table 8: Headline indicator for the 8th EAP – indicators highlighted in grey are directly relevant for agroforestry, indicators highlighted in green will show impacts of agroforestry

Indicator	Targets	Source
Climate change mitigation (Article 2(2)(a))		
1. Greenhouse gas emission (GHG, index 1990=100, tonnes of CO2 equivalent)	Climate neutrality: reduce net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030 from 1990 levels 21	EEA
2. GHG emissions from land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF, tonnes of CO2 equivalent)	Climate neutrality: increase net GHG removals by carbon sinks from the LULUCF sector to -310 million tonnes CO2 equivalent by 2030 23	EEA
Climate change adaptation (Article 2(2)(b))		
3. Climate-related economic losses (in EUR billion)	Economic impact of climate change: reduce overall monetary losses from weather and climate-related events	EEA
4. Drought impact on ecosystems (area affected in km2)	Ecosystem resilience: decrease the area impacted by drought and loss of vegetation productivity	EEA
A regenerative circular economy (Article 2(2)(c))		
5. Raw material consumption (tonnes per capita)	Material footprint: significantly decrease the EU's material footprint, by reducing the amount of raw material needed to produce the products consumed in the EU by reducing the amount of raw material needed to produce the products consumed in the Union	Eurostat
6. Total waste generation (kg per capita)	Waste prevention: significantly reduce the total amount of waste generated by 2030 26	Eurostat
Zero pollution and a toxic free environment (Article 2(2)(d))		
7. Premature deaths due to exposure to fine particulate matter (PM2.5) (number of premature deaths)	Environmental impact on health: reduce premature deaths from air pollution by 55% (from 2005 levels) by 2030	EEA
8. Nitrates in groundwater (mg of NO3/l and % monitoring stations with value above 50 mg NO3/l)	Clean water: reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% in safe groundwater resources	EEA
Biodiversity and ecosystems (Article 2(2)(e))		
9. Designated terrestrial and marine protected areas (% of total area)	Nature protection: legally protect at least 30% of the EU's land area and 30% of the EU's Sea area by 2030	EEA
10. Common bird index (index: 1990 = 100)	Biodiversity preservation: reverse the decline in populations of common birds	EBCC/ 32 BirdLife/ RSPB/CSO
11. Forest connectivity (0-100 %)	Healthy ecosystems: increase the degree of connectivity in forest ecosystems, with a view to creating and integrating ecological corridors and increase climate change resilience	Joint Research Centre
Environmental and climate pressures related to EU production and consumption (Article 2(2)(f))		
12. Energy consumption (in million tonnes of oil equivalent)	Energy efficiency: reduce (primary and final) energy consumption by at least 13% by 2030 compared to 2020	Eurostat

13. Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption (in %)	Sustainable energy: at least [45%] of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	Eurostat
14. Circular material use rate (in % to the overall material use)	Sustainable industry: double the ratio of circular material use by 2030 compared to 2020	Eurostat
15. Share of buses and trains in inland passenger transport (% of total inland passenger transport, expressed in passenger-kilometres)	Sustainable mobility: Increase the share of collective transport modes (buses, coaches and trains)	Eurostat
16. Area under organic farming (% of utilised agricultural area in km ²)	Sustainable agriculture: 25% of EU agricultural land organically farmed by 2030	Eurostat
Enabling conditions (Article 3)		
17. Share of environmental taxes in total tax revenues (in %)	Making polluters pay: increase the share of environmental taxes in total revenues from taxes and social contributions	Eurostat
18. Fossil fuel subsidies (EUR million) 40	Making polluters pay: reduce environmentally harmful subsidies, in particular fossil fuel subsidies, with a view to phasing them out without delay	European Commission
19. Environmental protection expenditure (EUR billion and % GDP)	Financing the transition: increase spending by households, corporations and governments on preventing, reducing and eliminating pollution and other environmental degradation	Eurostat
20. Green bonds (% of total bonds issued)	Sustainable investments: increase the issuance of green bonds to boost public and private financing for green investments	EEA
21. Eco-innovation index Member States' performance compared to EU average (EU = 100) and trend	Innovation for sustainability: increasing eco-innovation as a driver for the green transition	Eco-Innovation Observatory
Living well, within planetary boundaries (Article 2(1))		
22. Land take (km ² per year)	Planetary boundaries/sustainable use of land: no net land take by 2050	EEA
23. Water exploitation index plus (in %)	Planetary boundaries/sustainable use of water: reduce water scarcity	EEA
24. Consumption footprint (based on life cycle assessment)	Sustainable consumption: significantly decrease the EU's consumption footprint, i.e. the environmental impact of consumption	JRC
25. Employment and gross added value of environmental goods and services sector (% of total economy)	Sustainable competitiveness: increase of the shares of the green economy and of green employment in the whole economy	Eurostat
26. PLACEHOLDER Environmental inequalities	Environmental wellbeing: reduce environmental inequalities and ensure a fair transition	

Table 9: CAP Result Indicators – grey lines are relevant for agroforestry, light green lines are potentially relevant for agroforestry

Code	Result indicators (only based on interventions supported by the CAP)	
R.1PR	Enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation	Number of persons benefitting from advice, training, knowledge exchange or participating in European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational groups supported by the CAP in order to enhance sustainable economic, social, environmental, climate and resource efficiency performance
R.2	Linking advice and knowledge systems	Number of advisors receiving support to be integrated within the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)
R.3	Digitalising agriculture	Share of farms benefitting from support for digital farming technology through CAP
R.4	Linking income support to standards and good practices	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) covered by income support and subject to conditionality
R.5	Risk Management	Share of farms with supported CAP risk management tools
R.6PR	Redistribution to smaller farms	Percentage of additional direct payments per hectare for eligible farms below average farm size (compared to average)
R.7PR	Enhancing support for farms in areas with specific needs	Percentage additional support per hectare in areas with higher needs (compared to average)
R.8	Targeting farms in specific sectors	Share of farms benefitting from coupled income support for improving competitiveness, sustainability or quality
R.9PR	Farm modernisation	Share of farms receiving investment support to restructure and modernise, including to improve resource efficiency
R.10PR	Better supply chain organisation	Share of farms participating in producer groups, producer organisations, local markets, short supply chain circuits and quality schemes supported by the CAP
R.11	Concentration of supply	Share of value of marketed production by producer organisations or producers' groups with operational programmes in certain sectors
R.12	Adaptation to climate change	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to improve climate adaptation
R.13PR	Reducing emissions in the livestock sector	Share of livestock units (LU) under supported commitments to reduce emission of greenhouse gases and/or ammonia, including manure management
R.14PR	Carbon storage in soils and biomass	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to reduce emissions or to maintain or enhance carbon storage (including permanent grassland, permanent crops with permanent green cover, agricultural land in wetland and peatland)
5	Renewable energy from agriculture, forestry and from other renewable sources	Supported investments in renewable energy production capacity, including bio-based (in MW)
R.16	Investments related to climate	Share of farms benefitting from CAP investment support contributing to climate change mitigation and adaptation, and to the production of renewable energy or biomaterials
R.17PR	Afforested land	Area supported for afforestation, agroforestry and restoration, including breakdowns

R.18	Investment support to the forest sector	Total investment to improve the performance of the forestry sector
R.19PR	Improving and protecting soils	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments beneficial for soil management to improve soil quality and biota (such as reducing tillage, soil cover with crops, crop rotation included with leguminous crops)
R.20PR	Improving air quality	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to reduce ammonia emission
R.21PR	Protecting water quality	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for the quality of water bodies
R.22PR	Sustainable nutrient management	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments related to improved nutrient management
R.23PR	Sustainable water use	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to improve water balance
R.24PR	Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported specific commitments which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides in order to reduce risks and impacts of pesticides such as pesticides leakage
R.25	Environmental performance in the livestock sector	Share of livestock units (LU) under supported commitments to improve environmental sustainability
R.26	Investments related to natural resources	Share of farms benefitting from CAP productive and non-productive investment support related to care for the natural resources
R.27	Environmental or climate- related performance through investment in rural areas	Number of operations contributing to environmental sustainability and the achievement of climate mitigation and adaptation goals in rural areas
R.28	Environmental or climate- related performance through knowledge and innovation	Number of persons benefiting from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participating in European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational groups supported by the CAP related to environmental or climate-related performance
R.29PR	Development of organic agriculture	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) supported by the CAP for organic farming, with a split between maintenance and conversion
R.30PR	Connecting rural Europe	Share of forest land under commitments to support forest protection and management of ecosystem services
R.31PR	Preserving habitats and species	Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments supporting biodiversity conservation or restoration including high-nature-value farming practices
R.32	Investments related to biodiversity	Share of farms benefitting from CAP investment support contributing to biodiversity
R.33	Improving Natura 2000 management	Share of total Natura 2000 area under supported commitments
R.34PR	Preserving landscape features	Share of utilised agriculture area (UAA) under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees
R.35	Preserving beehives	Share of beehives supported by the CAP
R.36PR	Generational renewal	Number of young farmers benefitting from setting up with support from the CAP, including a gender breakdown
R.37	Growth and jobs in rural areas	New jobs supported in CAP projects
R.38	LEADER coverage	Share of rural population covered by local development strategies

R.39	Developing the rural economy	Number of rural businesses, including bio-economy businesses, developed with CAP support
R.40	Smart transition of the rural economy	Number of supported smart-village strategies
R.41PR	Connecting rural Europe	Share of rural population benefitting from improved access to services and infrastructure through CAP support
R.42	Promoting social inclusion	Number of persons covered by supported social inclusion projects
R.43PR	Limiting antimicrobial use	Share of livestock units (LU) concerned by supported actions to limit the use of antimicrobials (prevention/reduction)
R.44PR	Improving animal welfare	Share of livestock units (LU) covered by supported actions to improve animal welfare

Table 10: CAP Output indicators – grey lines are relevant for agroforestry

Output indicators	Type(s) of interventions
O.1 Number of European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational group projects	Cooperation (Article 77 of Regulation (EU) 2115/2021)
O.2 Number of advice actions or units to provide innovation support for preparing or implementing European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational group projects	Knowledge exchange and dissemination information (Article 78)
O.3 MO Number of CAP support beneficiaries	Horizontal indicator
O.4 Number of hectares benefitting from basic income support	Basic income support for sustainability
O.5 Number of beneficiaries or hectares benefitting from payments for small farmers	Payment for small farmers (Article 28)
O.6 Number of hectares benefitting from complementary income support for young farmers	Complementary income support for young farmers (Article 30)
O.7 Number of hectares benefitting from complementary redistributive income support	Complementary redistributive income support for sustainability (Article 29)
O.8 Number of hectares or of livestock units benefitting from eco-schemes	Schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare (Article 31)
O.9 Number of units covered by supported CAP risk management tools	Risk management (Article 76)
O.10 Number of hectares benefitting from coupled income support	Coupled income support (Article 32)
O.11 Number of heads benefitting from coupled income support	Coupled income support (Article 32)
O.12 Number of hectares benefitting from support for areas facing natural or other specific constraints, including a breakdown per type of area	Natural or other area-specific constraints (Article 71)
O.13 Number of hectares benefitting from support under Natura 2000 or Directive 2000/60/EC	Area-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements (Article 72)
O.14 Number of hectares (excluding forestry) or number of other units covered by environmental or climate-related commitments going beyond mandatory requirements	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)
O.15 Number of hectares (forestry) or number of other units covered by environmental or climate-related commitments going beyond mandatory requirements	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)
O.16 Number of hectares or number of other units under maintenance commitments for afforestation and agroforestry	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)

O.17 Number of hectares or number of other units benefitting from support for organic farming	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)
O.18 Number of livestock units (LU) benefitting from support for animal welfare, health or increased biosecurity measures	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)
O.19 Number of operations or units supporting genetic resources	Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (Article 70)
O.20 Number of supported on-farm productive investment operations or units	Investments (Articles 73 and 74)
O.21: Number of supported on-farm non-productive investment operations or units	Investments (Articles 73 and 74)
O.22 Number of supported infrastructure investment operations or units	Investments (Articles 73 and 74)
O.23 Number of supported off-farm non-productive investment operations or units	Investments (Articles 73 and 74)
O.24 Number of supported off-farm productive investment operations or units	Investments (Articles 73 and 74)
O.25 Number of young farmers receiving setting-up support	Setting up of young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-up (Article 75)
O.26 Number of new farmers receiving setting-up support (other than young farmers reported under O.25)	Setting up of young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-up (Article 75)
O.27 Number of rural businesses receiving support for start up	Setting up of young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-up (Article 75)
O.28 Number of supported producer groups and producer organisations	Cooperation (Article 77)
O.29 Number of beneficiaries receiving support to participate in official quality schemes	Cooperation (Article 77)
O.30 Number of supported operations or units for generational renewal (excluding setting-up support)	Cooperation (Article 77)
O.31 Number of supported local development strategies (LEADER) or preparatory actions	Cooperation (Article 77)
O.32 Number of supported other cooperation operations or units (excluding EIP reported under O.1)	Cooperation (Article 77)
O.33 Number of supported training, advice and awareness actions or units	Knowledge exchange and dissemination of information (Article 78)
O.34 MO Number of hectares under environmental practices (summary indicator on physical area covered by conditionality, eco-schemes, agri- and forest-environment-climate management commitments)	Horizontal indicator
O.35 Number of supported operational programmes	Types of intervention in certain sectors (Article 47)
O.36 Number of actions or units supported in the wine sector	Types of interventions in the wine sector (Article 58)
O.37 Number of actions or units for beekeeping preservation or improvement	Types of interventions in the apiculture sector (Article 55)

Table 11: CAP Impact Indicators

	Impact Indicator code	Context Indicator Code	Context Indicator Code	Indicator name
		PMEF	CMEF current	
Population		C.01	C.01	Total population
		C.02	C.04	Population density
		C.03	C.02	Age structure of the population
Total area		C.04	C.03	Total area
		C.05	C.31	Land cover
Labour market	I.24	C.06	C.05	Employment rate in rural areas
		C.07	C.07	Unemployment rate in rural areas
		C.08	C.11	Employment
		C.08	C.11	Employment by sector
		C.08	C.11	Employment by type of region
		C.08	C.13	Employment by economic activity
Economy	I.25	C.09	C.08	GDP per capita
	I.27	C.10	C.09	Poverty rate
		C.11	C.10	Gross value added
		C.11	C.10	Gross value added by sector
	I.8	C.11	R.03_PI	In agriculture, Gross value added for primary producers
Farms and farmers		C.12	C.17	Agricultural holdings (farms)
		C.13	C.22	Farm labour force
		C.14	C.23	Age structure of farm managers
		C.15	C.24	Agricultural training of farm managers
	I.23	C.16		New farm managers and new young farm managers
Agricultural land		C.17	C.18	Utilised agricultural area
		C.18	C.20	Irrigable land
		C.19	C.34	Farming in Natura 2000 areas
		C.20	C.32	Areas facing natural and other specific constraints
	I.21	C.21		Agricultural land covered with landscape features
	I.22	C.22	R.11	Crop diversity
Livestock		C.23	C.21	Livestock units
		C.24		Livestock density
	I.3	C.25	C.25	Agricultural factor income

Agricultural and farm income	I.2	C.26	C.26	Comparison of agricultural income with non-agricultural labour costs
		C.27		Farm income
	I.4			Farm income by type of farming
	I.4			Farm income by region
	I.4			Farm income by farm size
	I.5			Farm income in areas facing natural and other specific constraints
		C.28	C.28	Gross fixed capital formation in agriculture
Agricultural productivity	I.6	C.29	C.27	Total factor productivity in agriculture
		C.30	C.14	Labour productivity in agriculture
		C.30	C.15	Labour productivity in forestry
		C.30	C.16	Labour productivity in the food industry
Agricultural trade	I.7	C.31	I.06	Agricultural imports and exports
Other gainful activities		C.32	C.30	Tourism infrastructure
Farming practices		C.33	C.19	Agricultural area under organic farming
		C.34	C.33	Farming intensity
	I.29	C.35	R.09_PI	Value of production under Union quality schemes and of organic production
Biodiversity	I.19	C.36	C.35	Farmland Bird Index
	I.20	C.37		Percentage of species and habitats of Community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends
Water	I.17	C.38		Water use in agriculture
	I.15	C.39		Water quality
	I.15	C.39	C.40	Gross nutrient balance – nitrogen
	I.15	C.39	C.40	Gross nutrient balance – phosphorus
	I.16	C.39		Nitrates in groundwater
Soil	I.11	C.40	C.41	Soil organic carbon in agricultural land
	I.13	C.41	C.42	Soil erosion by water
Energy	I.12	C.42	C.43	Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry
		C.43	C.44	Energy use in agriculture, forestry
Climate	I.10	C.44	C.45	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture
	I.9	C.45		Agricultural sector resilience progress indicator
		C.46		Direct agricultural loss attributed to disasters
Air	I.14	C.47	C.45	Ammonia emissions from agriculture
Health	I.28	C.48		Sales/use of antimicrobials in food producing animals

	I.18	C.49		Risk, use and impacts of pesticides
Modernisation	I.1			Share of CAP budget for knowledge sharing and innovation
Fairness	I.26			Distribution of CAP support

Table 12: Soil monitoring law indicators

Degradation factors	Soil descriptors
Soil erosion	Soil erosion rate (tonnes of loss soil per hectare per year)
Loss of soil organic carbon	Soil organic carbon concentration (g per kg)
Soil compaction	Bulk density in topsoils (g cm ⁻³)
Excess nutrient content in soil	Available phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹); total nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹)
Soil contamination	Concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cr (VI), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (µg per kg), concentration of a selection of organic contaminants (done by Member States); pesticides candidates for substitution and substances authorised under emergency regime and biocides residues; per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) total and sum of PFAS total
Reduction of soil capacity to retain water	Water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of volume of water); volume of saturated soil
Acidification	Soil acidity (pH H ₂ O)
Soil ecological functions	
Soil aggregation	Water-stable aggregates (%)
Soil respiration	Soil microbial basal respiration (µl O ₂ h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ soil dry weight)
Soil biomass	Soil microbial biomass carbon (C _{mic} µg Cg ⁻¹ soil dry weight)
Soil biodiversity	
Taxonomic diversity	Diversity of soil organisms through (presence counts per taxonomic group based on metabarcoding)
Population abundance	Total abundances of bacteria and archaea; total abundances of fungi; total number and proportion of pathogenic fungi; total nematode abundance per functional group based on morphology
Soil habitat	
Soil structure	Size class proportions (sand, silt, clay); proportion of coarse materials (>2mm)